

Importance of Mental Health Education in College Curriculum

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ABSTRACT

*This paper attempts to study how **curriculum** is based on following modules Positive Psychology, Social Emotional Learning, Social Psychology and Mental Health Literacy can be adopted for colleges. When one hears the word 'curriculum' in the context of mental health, it might seem bewildering. What could the contents be and how would this be imparted to school students? First, why is it important? Data shows the growing prevalence of mental illnesses, especially among children and adolescents. Close to 15 million individuals are battling some form of mental health related illness or other in India; 10% of all children suffer from some form of mental health issue and more than 50% of these go untreated. Many more are undetected. Depression is now the single largest illness in the world; suicide is the second leading cause of death among adolescents and young adults; and almost half of all mental illnesses begin by the age of 14. At the same time, the psychosocial stressors experienced by children cannot be ignored either. These include the growing pressure of academics and competitive entrance examinations, and even exposure to media, which seems to invade almost every aspect of our lives. Children and adolescents are particularly vulnerable given the impact on their self-esteem, and a positive body image contributing to overall psychological well-being.*

Adolescence and young adulthood are globally recognized as periods marked by opportunities for development and the emergence of mental health vulnerabilities. The high prevalence of common mental health problems during adolescence and young adulthood, the substantial treatment gap, and multiple barriers to help-seeking at this age highlight the need for comprehensive, campus-based youth mental health approaches grounded in sociocultural realities. India has one of the largest higher education systems globally, as well as a high proportion of youth, demographically. According to the 2018-2019 All India Survey on Higher Education, there are 993 universities and an average of 28 colleges per lakh of the eligible youth population. About 37.4 million youth are enrolled in institutes of higher education in India. This scenario presents both opportunities and challenges for addressing youth mental health needs.

Keywords: India, intersectoral coordination, school mental health, health education, Curriculum

1. INTRODUCTION

mental health curriculum ought not to be viewed as increasing the academic burden of subjects being taught. Instead, its aim should be to highlight the need for incorporating life-skills training as an integral aspect of schooling. Some of these life skills could include encouraging them to acquire skills related to gender sensitivity, dealing with bullying and managing aggression, improving emotional intelligence while imbibing skills for emotional regulation, building empathy, training them to be assertive and, making them media literate.

Being mindful of such a curricular inclusion does not necessarily entail an additional number of academic classes or teaching hours. Instead it could involve more experiential and fun-learning techniques which are enjoyable for both teachers as well as students. This serves the dual purpose of equipping young minds with the necessary skills to improve their overall quality of life in the future, as well as building their resilience to deal with the world and its challenges in the years ahead. These practical experiences and learning are what help develop their personality. Therefore, such experiential learning cannot be restricted to textbooks.

Ideally, a mental health curriculum needs to be running in parallel with the existing educational paradigm within schools. Mental health often tends to get neglected when compared to the significance typically attached to general-health awareness (hygiene and sanitation, nutrition and balanced diets, education about infectious and communicable diseases). A point to be reiterated is that similar to physical ailments, mental illness is also rooted in a biological basis, as opposed to mythological beliefs which attribute mental illnesses to the presence of evil spirits, or the like. Given the extent of stigmatization of mental illnesses, a catalyst for change would need to begin at the roots. This is by sensitizing the young minds of children as well as adolescents. By incorporating mental health as an integral part of our health curriculum, such a pedagogy, which sensitizes young minds about mental health and shapes their attitudes and beliefs, would help seize the future of mental health in the country. It is the parents that fall prey to them first. To truly help children, it is critical that parents make a conscientious effort to approach the mental health of their children with empathy and concern. Parents must come to terms with the realities of the present generation. They face far more challenges than the parents did when they were growing up. Building a collaborative relationship between the school and the parents is extremely crucial to the success of any mental health curriculum.

Last, but not the least, the objective of introducing a mental health curriculum is to encourage help-seeking behaviour, especially in connection with mental health. It is through the training of young children and adolescents during their prime years that we can improve their own psychological well-being. The long-term implications of incorporating such a curriculum within schools will contribute to a society which is educated, informed and sensitized towards mental health

2.OBJECTIVE:

This paper intends to explore and analyze *curriculum* that can have substantial influence on well-being of the students. Also, college curriculum should strive with conscious effort to constantly promote *mental health* and health education and should be part of the general health *curriculum*.

3.MENTAL HEALTH AND JUSTICE PROGRAM WITHIN CURRICULUM:

Merely 4 countries in the entire world have a total population of 250 million. India, on the other hand, has 250 million children just in school. Unfortunately, 12% of Indian children between the ages of 4 and 16 suffer from psychiatric disorders. 12% of 250 million is a staggering number – just do the math. Children have complex but fragile eco-systems that can easily fall prey to a host of behavioural, emotional, learning or mental disorders. In fact, up to 50% of mental, behavioural and psychological problems have their onset during adolescence. The most common mental health issues that youngsters tend to face are: anxiety disorders, depression and eating disorders, along with psychosis and ADHD – these two often being co-morbid. Resulting out of these, are what we call co-occurring disorders that include substance abuse and certain behavioural disorders. The stories of young kids attempting suicide are the most shocking and horrifying. At an age when children should be running around, playing games and having loads of fun without a care in the world, what would prompt them to even think about something as drastic and dark as ending their lives? It is the combined duty of parents, teachers and educational institutions to ensure the holistic development of children on a physical, emotional and mental level. Mental wellbeing is the key to unlocking the unique potential in every child and in ensuring that they can live their life to the fullest. Assessing every child's state of mind and coping mechanisms at every stage of their formative years and taking the requisite measures to enhance them holds the key to sustained mental wellbeing throughout their lives. Unfortunately, teachers and school managements have traditionally not been equipped to deal with mental health issues or to manage the emotional well-being of students. For example, children have always been pulled up for disruptive behaviour. But now, we need to have an understanding of mental health-related symptoms and signs to analyse the reason behind such behaviour before deciding what should be done about it. Similarly, teachers don't know that children can be afflicted by the same mental disorders as adults, but their symptoms may be drastically different. Psychosocial Development refers to Erik Erickson's theory of psychological development of an individual in interaction with his or her social environment and relationships at different stages in life. At every stage, kids experience a conflict that becomes a turning point in their development. These conflicts either help them develop a positive psychological quality or result in the failure to do so. When children deal successfully with a conflict, they emerge with strong psychological skills that can serve them for the rest of their lives.

These skills allow for competence and motivate positive behaviours and actions. Also, it is a myth that only children who have learning, behavioural or emotional issues fall prey to mental health concerns. Dr. Stephen Chou, who served on the board of directors at SENG (Supporting Emotional Needs of the Gifted), wrote an article where he explained how even gifted children can break down when they experience failure. Sometimes, it takes only one failure for them to believe that they're not really that gifted or good enough. After that, they may experience shame, doubt, inferiority and even guilt. This is where the proper psychosocial development of a child becomes vital, not just the enhancement of their other skills and talents. As an educationist and mental health activist, I've always believed that mental health education needs to be an integral part of the school curriculum. The time has now come to translate advocacy into tangible action. Both children and teachers must understand what mental health is and how important it is to the overall growth of children. The 2014 Indian National Youth Policy incorporates objectives such as developing a healthy generation and promoting community service. Several governmental youth development programs (eg, Nehru Yuva Kendra Sangathan, National Service Scheme) promote leadership qualities and administration abilities. Engaging young people and faculty in national concerns along with the provision of opportunities for community service are advocated in the draft of the 2019 National Educational Policy in India, which laments the current rigid boundaries of disciplines, an exam-centric approach, and inadequate psychological support for students in higher education. This new policy and the University Grants Commission (UGC) guidelines indicate that student counseling systems must be in place in institutes of higher education (IHE), and teacher-counselors need to be trained to offer psychological support to youth. Also, the UGC recommends setting up student counseling centers. However, there have been gaps in the implementation of relevant policies and programs. Unfortunately, there are no data on the uniform implementation of such guidelines across IHE. Field observations suggest that, while several institutes have made provisions for counseling services in some way, there are no

systems in place to continuously capture the nature and quality of services offered, nor do they gather and assess student perspectives on ease of access and utility. In several instances, counseling services when available tend to have suboptimal uptake.

A continuum approach to mental health care is needed—an approach that includes promotive and preventive universal programs for all college youth, along with targeted intervention options for those experiencing significant distress and mental health problems. Such a system should offer targeted interventions across a spectrum of intensity, starting with structured self-help modules for common mental health concerns, peer support systems, and mentor support for mental health in addition to easily accessible counseling services, and timely referrals to specialized mental health professional services. Currently, access to such a range of interventions is highly variable across institutes. Although there are UGC guidelines for the inclusion of youth development components in student induction and mentoring sessions, the uniform inclusion of a standardized training module on mentoring for mental health is needed for faculty in IHE.

Most importantly, the mere availability of counseling services would be insufficient for ensuring uptake and desired mental health outcomes. Apart from reducing scarcity in the supply of resources (eg, trained personnel), the system should foster innovations to handle demand-side barriers (eg, perceived low need and stigma). Even when multilevel services are available for youth in distress, the services are unlikely to be used unless they are embedded in an enabling environment that helps break psychosocial barriers to help-seeking and promotes a positive mental health culture on campus.

4.OPPORTUNITIES WITHIN CAMPUS:

An environment that promotes mental health care can be facilitated through youth engagement programs focused on mental health themes. Initiatives that engage youth volunteers, by familiarizing them with the continuum approach to mental health and inspire those youth to carry out activities that destigmatize mental health and professional help-seeking amongst peers can play an important role. Youth volunteers could also be trained to serve as gatekeepers and first-line support providers. While such youth-driven initiatives should engage youth across varied streams of study, these could be particularly useful for students in the field of psychology and related disciplines. Many colleges have students enrolled in psychology courses who could benefit from such training and inclusion of action projects on mental health promotion and peer support in their curricula. In addition to addressing unmet youth mental health needs, this strategy can also provide students of psychology a hands-on experience in applying their knowledge in a real-world context, allowing them to work with peers on challenges such as stigma and the hidden burdens related to mental health.

There is a severe shortage of trained mental health resources in India; this shortage partially drives the insufficient engagement of professionals in systematic efforts towards de-stigmatization of mental health and promotive interventions. Large-scale, uniform implementation of youth engagement for mental health initiatives across IHE could be a cost-effective way to address this gap. The 2019 National Educational Policy recommends that, to the extent possible, youth engagement in community service should be integrated within the curriculum, and the time allotted for social engagement for each student should be at least equal to a full semester across the duration of the course. This provides a big window of opportunity for training volunteer-youth for mental health promotion on campus.

Counselors and interested faculty could be trained to set up mental health promotion systems on campuses and bring about systemic changes rather than limiting their role to offering one-to-one counseling services to those who approach or are referred to them. Field observations suggest that universal promotive intervention programs are likely to be well received by college youth when offered on youth-centric themes and involve choice-based enrollment. Interested faculty could be trained using a “training of trainers” cascade model to provide brief promotive modules on a predetermined set of mental health themes. Promotive interventions strengthen protective factors and resilience, and they serve as gateways for youth to negotiate professional help-seeking for mental health.

5.PATHWAYS TO THE FUTURE- IMPLICATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION:

A cursory scan of the global initiatives for youth mental health reveals massive funding support across nations for large-scale implementation and continuous monitoring. In India, although there is a growing recognition of youth mental health needs by policymakers, faculty, and administrators; the will to invest in broad-based mental health initiatives within campuses on a sustained basis is considerably weak, partially due to perceived limitations in feasibility, a lack of conviction, and competing academics and other programs. Specific mandates and support from regulatory bodies, advocacy efforts by mental health professionals, and incentivization of such efforts by institutes can help address this situation. There is a need for advocacy and sensitizing of stakeholders in the higher education

system in India for making space to implement the frameworks that legitimize and prioritize multipronged mental health promotion systems for college youth. Active involvement of mental health professionals is required in garnering support and buy-in from the educational sector. This can be achieved through synthesizing data available from various countries on the psychosocial and economic benefits of investing in youth mental health and the different ways in which such programs are being implemented globally in IHE.

The digital pathway is another underutilized route to address unmet mental health needs in Indian IHE. Despite good internet penetration, high engagement of youth in online platforms, and the potential flexibility and appeal of digital health tools, there is a scarcity of research-backed mental health tools developed by or in collaboration with mental health professionals in India. Their scalability and acceptability potential are tremendous and need to be optimally utilized. A youth-centric, comprehensive digital platform across IHE can serve as an essential resource for youth who may be exploring mental health information and care options for themselves and others. This could be a multifunction platform accessible to all youth in IHE that provides information, resources, credible links to self-help material, and opportunities to connect to trained peer supporters and counselors online and gives access to a directory of professional services. These tools can also serve as channels for de-stigmatization and positive shifts in perceived peer norms related to professional help-seeking.

6.CONCLUSION:

In low resource contexts, the utilization and mobilization of existing support structures in educational institutes can enhance feasibility, receptivity, scalability, and sustainability of promotive programs for youth. Youth engagement in mental health initiatives, universal promotive interventions, and the optimum use of digital platforms are interlinked, underutilized, and scalable approaches to campus mental health promotion in India. These would be in alignment with the visions of the national youth policy and the recent draft of national education policy in India. These have the potential to reduce the wide treatment gap for common mental health problems as well as empower youth and campus communities to promote youth mental health in general.

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